

Polarographic behavior of Cu^{II}-theophylline complex

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Abstract : The Cu^{II}-theophylline complex is best formed at pH 4.5. The Cu^{II}-theophylline complex formed is in 1 : 1 ratio. The system is irreversible and the kinetic and thermodynamic parameters have been determined.

Keywords : Cu^{II}-theophylline complex, polarography, kinetics, thermodynamics.

Introduction

Theophylline (1,3-dimethyl-1-*H*-purine-2,6-dione) has been used in the treatment of the asthma as an alternative to prophylactic drugs¹ and act as a stimulator of the central nervous system. Several methods for determination of Cu^{II}-theophylline complex have been reported².

In this work, the optimum conditions for the determination of Cu^{II}-theophylline complex have been investigated using DC polarography.

Experimental

Apparatus :

The DC recording polarograph (CL 357) of Elico limited was used for study. The three electrode system was completed using a working electrode (D.M.E.), reference electrode (saturated calomel electrode) and counter electrode (platinum electrode). A polarographic capillary 120 mm long and 0.05 mm in diameter was used. The $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$ value was 2.376 mg^{2/3} s^{1/4} at 65 cm effective height of mercury reservoir.

A digital pH meter model 111E was used for measuring the pH of the analytes.

Reagents :

All the solutions were prepared from doubly distilled water and analytical reagent grade chemicals (Merck). Theophylline {Sidmak Laboratories (India)} solution was prepared freshly every 5 days. CuCl₂.2H₂O used was of analytical reagent grade.

Procedure :

The general procedure for DC polarography is as follows. A 10 ml of experimental solution was placed in a polarographic cell and deoxygenated with nitrogen for 15 min. The cell was placed in the thermostat and the capillary was inserted in solution. The current voltage curves were measured manually. The potential was applied to the working electrode with 150 mV/min scan rate and 100 nA/div sensitivity of current measurement.

Results and discussion

A well defined reversible and diffusion controlled wave for Cu^{II} was observed in 0.1 M acetate buffer at pH 4.5. The value of $E_{1/2}^{\text{reversible}}$ for Cu^{II} was found to be - 0.07 volt vs SCE.

Shift in half wave potential of Cu^{II} towards negative potential and decrease in the diffusion current with increase in the concentration of theophylline confirm complex formation. This is partly because of the Cu^{II}-theophylline system is much more stable than the simple aqua Cu^{II} ion and partly because of this ligand is much poorer bridge for electron transfer than a water molecule and increases the activation energy involved in reduction³. Cu^{II} undergoes one electron reduction with theophylline. The plot of $\log(i/(i_d - i))$ vs E were linear with slope 65 ± 5 mV, which suggests that electrode reaction is irreversible. The variation of current and potential of the Cu^{II}-theophylline complex as function of pH, temperature, concentration and constituents of the supporting electrolytes solutions were measured by DC polarography.

Changes in the nature and concentration of the supporting electrolytes may affect half wave potential. The response was examined in presence of different buffer solutions e.g. B.R. buffer, acetate buffer etc. and different supporting electrolytes e.g. KCl, KNO₃, HCl etc. (Table 1). Acetate buffer was selected as the optimum because it gave the highest response and good reproducibility. The half wave potential and diffusion current of Cu^{II}-theophylline system strongly depends on the pH of the

potential of the system becomes more negative. It means that H⁺ ion involves in reaction mechanism. The best wave was observed in pH 4.5, so this pH was selected in subsequent work.

A gradual change in diffusion current and half wave potential was observed when the solution temperature was decreased from 35 to 15 °C (Table 2). When we decreased the temperature of solution, the half wave potential of system becomes more negative. In this system the temperature coefficient is greater than 3 mV per degree so that the system is irreversible⁴.

The nature of the C-V curve of Cu^{II}-theophylline complex was irreversible. As the theophylline concentration increases the irreversibility of the electrode reaction increases because the formal rate constant decreases gradually. Kinetic parameters (K_{fn}^0 , αn) were calculated by Meites and Israel's method and Gaur and Bhargava's method⁶.

The plot of $\log K_{fn}^0$ vs $1/T$ is found to be linear from the slope of which the values of ΔH_p^\ddagger , ΔH_v^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger have been evaluated and presented in Table 3.

A perusal of the values of various quantities presented in Table 3 shows that activation free energy change (ΔG^\ddagger) is positive at all the temperatures suggesting the non spontaneous nature of electrode process. Positive value of ΔS^\ddagger suggests that formation of activated state is accompanied by the increase of entropy¹⁰.

Table 1. Effect of supporting electrolyte on diffusion current and half wave potential of the Cu^{II}-theophylline complex
[Theophylline] = $3.56 \times 10^{-3} M$, [CuCl₂.2H₂O] = $1.25 \times 10^{-4} M$
and Temp. = 35 °C

Sl. no.	Supporting electrolyte	$i_d \times 100$ (nA)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	$-\Delta E_{1/2}$ (V)
1.	0.1 M Acetate buffer (pH 4.5)	1.1	0.214	0.144
2.	1 M HCl	0.8	0.150	0.090
3.	0.5 M KCl	0.4	0.230	0.195

where, i_d = diffusion current, $E_{1/2}$ = half wave potential, $\Delta E_{1/2}$ = difference in $E_{1/2}$ of Cu^{II} and Cu^{II}-theophylline complex.

solution. No polarographic wave was observed at pH > 7 (ppt. formation takes place in basic medium). A gradual change in diffusion current and half wave potential were observed when the solution pH was increased from 2.5 to 6.5. When we increase the pH of solution then half wave

Table 2. Effect of temperature on Cu^{II}-theophylline complex in 0.1 M acetate buffer solution at pH 4.5

[Theophylline] = $3.56 \times 10^{-3} M$, [CuCl₂.2H₂O] = $1.25 \times 10^{-4} M$ and pH 4.5

Sl. no.	T (K)	$i_d \times 100$ (nA)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	$-\Delta E_{1/2}$ (V)	αn	K_{fn}^0 (cm/s)	D (cm ² /s)
1.	308	1.2	0.214	0.144	0.887	6.67×10^{-5}	4.04×10^{-2}
2.	303	0.9	0.220	0.150	0.851	4.90×10^{-5}	2.28×10^{-2}
3.	298	0.7	0.224	0.154	1.000	7.94×10^{-6}	1.37×10^{-2}
4.	293	0.5	0.237	0.166	0.946	4.90×10^{-6}	6.99×10^{-3}
5.	288	0.3	0.265	0.195	0.491	1.26×10^{-2}	2.52×10^{-3}

where, K_{fn}^0 = formal rate constant obtained from Meites and Israel's method, D = diffusion coefficient, αn = transfer coefficient.

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters at different temperatures

Sl. no.	T (K)	$\Delta H_p^\ddagger \times 10^5$ (J/mol)	$\Delta H_v^\ddagger \times 10^5$ (J/mol)	$\Delta G^\ddagger \times 10^4$ (J/mol)	$\Delta S^\ddagger \times 10^2$ (J/K)
1.	308	1.45	1.4236	2.38	3.85
2.	303	1.45	1.4241	2.37	3.92
3.	298	1.45	1.4245	2.52	3.93
4.	293	1.45	1.4249	2.53	4.00
5.	288	1.45	1.4254	1.67	4.37

Evidences :

The complexation of copper(II) ion with theophylline at pH 7 was studied with the aid of conductometric, potentiometric and spectrophotometric titrations and infrared spectroscopy². Both conductometric (or potentiometric) titration and spectrophotometric titration indicated 1 mole of cupric ion combines with 1 mole theophylline. It is of particular interest to note that the cupric ion combines with theophylline but not with caffeine. Theophylline and caffeine have similar structures except that the former has methyl group at N-1 and N-3 leaving N-7 free while the latter has three methyl groups occupying all three positions at N-1, N-3 and N-7 (Fig. 1). From this

Fig. 1. Structure of theophylline and caffeine.

result, it is indicated that N-7 and the keto group at C-6 are involved in complexation².

The evidence shown in the infrared spectra indicates that the metal is attached to both the oxygen at C-6 and N-7. In this case, the C=O stretching vibration band diminished on complexing with cupric ion², which suggests that the C-6 lost keto group character on complexing; therefore the most probable mechanism² is proposed and shown in Fig. 2.

Conclusions :

It is clear from the study that the shift of $E_{1/2}$ becomes negative on adding of theophylline to Cu^{II}, which confirms complex formation. Cu^{II} forms 1 : 1 complex with theophylline. The properties of complex were strongly dependent upon both temperature and pH. The kinetic parameters (K^0_m , α_n) and thermodynamic parameters ($\Delta H^{\#}_p$, $\Delta H^{\#}_v$, $\Delta G^{\#}$, $\Delta S^{\#}$) of Cu^{II}-theophylline complex were determined by employing the polarographic technique at pH 4.5 and in 0.1 M acetate buffer at different temperatures (from 25 to 35 °C).

Fig. 2. The proposed mechanism for copper-theophylline formation is illustrated here.

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